

THE STUDY OF PHYTONYMS IN LINGUISTIC RESEARCH PROCESSES

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Abstract: This article provides feedback on the use of phytonyms and their description in research, as well as on the research of Uzbek scientists in this regard.

Keywords: linguistics, phytonyms, translation, translation transformations, equivalent, scientific analysis.

In linguistics, it is known that almost all works from folklore to modern literature mention phytonyms (names of trees, flowers, plants). Phytonyms are connotative in nature and have great metaphorical potential. In the study of phytonyms, two directions can be distinguished: the directions of using linguistic and phytonyms as a metaphorical element of comparison.

Despite the active use of the term "phytonym" in linguistics since the 70s of the 20th century, there is no generally accepted interpretation of the term in linguistics. A. M. Based on letova's work "from the history of the study of phytonymic vocabulary: the linguoculturological aspect", we will briefly talk about the emergence and development of the term "phytonym". The term phytonym means "semantic commonality of the names of trees, grasses, shrubs, flowers, berries, vegetables and other crops", in addition to this term, the researcher gives the decoding of the term "phytonymy" – "phytonymic set of units".

According to research, the first attempts to interpret phytonym were made in separate articles, in which the term expressed the names of "individual plants", viz. "phytonymy", a collection of plant world truth names, was regarded as a special branch of onomastics – the science of linguistics. Engaged in the study of their own names. Also, researchers give a definition of the term phytonymic unit, by which the name of all combinations of words of a particular thematic layer means: phytonyms themselves, names of plant parts, collective names, Latin adjectives, etc.

In the context of linguistic analysis, the phytonym was first used in A.V. It was used by Superanskaya in the book of the general theory of her name, in which a narrow interpretation of this concept was discussed on the example of studying the names of plants, such as Royal Oak, weeping tree, etc.

Later, the phytonym was used in the quality of its name of any plant. Phytonym is also widely considered to be the "terminological name of all plants".

In the 90s of the 20th century, the term phytonym was broadly reinforced by the lexicographic practice of etymological dictionaries, and was used with the names "Scholar neologism", "Greek compound phytonym" plant, and onyma, plant.

Some researchers found that a.M. In the aforementioned work, Letova states that at the end of the century there was an increased interest in the study of phytonymy in linguistic and ethnolinguistic aspects.

The world of plants is one of the riches of nature. Our people, from the earliest times, tried to know the peculiarities of plants and used them to treat various diseases. Our great allomas, such as Abu Rayhan Beruniy, Abu Bakr ar-Roziy, Abu Ali Ibn Sino, were those who tried to treat the pain of patients with medicinal plants. Peoples living in the regions of Central Asia, Caucasus, Iran, Afghanistan, Egypt, Asia Minor tried to study the distribution, growth and characteristics of plants in their territories even about 5-6 thousand years ago. The great alloma Abu Rayhon Beruniy recorded several works covering the history, culture, fauna and the Nabot world of that time. These include works such as "chronology", "India", "Geodesy", "minerology", "Massoud's law", "Saydana". Of particular note is his work "Kitab asSaydana fi-t tibb", written in 1048 in darwri, the Sultanate of Ma'dud, the successor of Mahmud Ghaznavi, in the last years of his life. The work is devoted to the description of medicinal plants, animals and Madans. A valuable aspect of "Saydana" is that it lists the names of medicinal plants in several languages. In this work, Berunius gave a complete description of the medicinal plants growing in the East, especially in Central Asia. In particular, the work describes 1116 species of Medicine. Of this, 750 species are from plants, 101 species are from animals, the remaining 255 species are from minerals. We will introduce you to several of the medicinal phytonyms that berunius commented on: he also quotes Abu Ali ibn Sina, our great allomamiz, in his works such as "the laws of Tib" and "Kitabush-healing", about the properties of many medicinal plants growing in Central Asia. Moreover, Babur, who left an indelible mark on history as a mature manifestation of the field of language and medicine, as an allome praising the beauty of Man and nature, also cited the animal and nabobot world with deep scientific explanations in his work "Baburnoma". Some phytonyms growing in India were first cited in the work "The Beaver".

Even today, interest in phytomins in our country is great. Not only biologists and zoologists, connoisseurs of medicine, but also linguistic scientists were interested in healing plants and wrote various brochures. In Particular, D."Herbalism" Of Yormatova, H.Placidev's "plant diseases", N.Öljaboyeva's" jewels from the treasury of folk medicine and, in addition, many dictionaries were written.

The phytonymic study in Uzbek is also grammatically, lexically, semantically significant, and in determining their content, an in-depth analysis of plant names helps. The plant names we mentioned above look different from the current era plant names both in pronunciation and in terms of naming. We now call some phytonyms with previous names, now with other names. Linguistic research on dictionary units representing plant names has observed the use of terms such as plant name, plant lexemes representing plants, plant horses, plants naming horses, botanical terms, phytonym, phytonymic lexicon, Floristic lexicon. The meaning content of some of these units, mutual G.Ne ' Matova was analyzed in the dissertation. Fitonim Greek Phutonosimlik + onoma is a horse with a horse, bionim (yun.biog-bios, life+onomaname) s. The term phytonym as a scientific neologism arose in Russian linguistics in the 70s of the 20th century, later it was absorbed into Uzbek onomastics. For example, in Uzbekistan, apricot has names such as Okurik, Shalakh, Ruhi Juvanon, Mohtobi Ahrory, Subhani, Gulungi, Koorsadiq, Khurmoi, Isfarak, Javpazak, etc. These names are phytonyms as a name with a special name that represents apricot varieties, as opposed to apricot appellative. Phytonyms have not been extensively studied in Uzbek onomastic sources. But there are a wide range of scientific-theoretical and practical issues that phytonymy studies. Phytonymy deals with the following issues related to phytonyms:

- 1) *proverbial names of plants-linguistic, nonlinear factors of the appearance and formation of phytonyms;*
- 2) *historical, folk traditions regarding the naming of plants;*
- 3) *the function of phytonymic indicators in the composition of lysonic properties and phytonyms;*
- 4) *naming principles of plants;*
- 5) *historical and modern forms of phytonyms and linguistic changes in phytonyms;*
- 6) *lexicon-meaning properties of phytonyms; morphemic and facsimile models of phytonyms;*
- 8) *the relationship between the appellative lexicon of the language and the phytonymic lexicon;*
- 9) *other bionym types of phytonyms: anthroponyms and zoonyms, their relationship with ornithonyms and the task transitions in it;*
- 10) *folklore, history with the creation of phytonyms in works on botany and ancient manuscripts;*
- 11) *features of phytonyms regarding local dialects and dialects;*
- 12) *the etymology of phytonyms;*
- 13) *scientific and practical issues related to the classification of phytonyms;*
- 14) *must learn the principles of phytonymic mapping and dictionary construction.*

Phytonymy has its own object and subject of study as a branch of onomastics. Hence, phytonymy is also considered one of the areas of linguistics with theoretical and practical significance. The names of plants are phytonyms, the set of which is called phytonymy. The field of phytonymy of the Uzbek language is one of the areas that need to be studied even more widely.

References:

1. Madaliyeva.Y., O'zbek tilida fitonimlarning leksik-semantik va tematik xususiyatlari// "PEDAGOGS" international research journal ISSN: 2181-4027_ SJIF:4.995- www.pedagoglar.uz-Volume-23, Issue-1, December -202269
2. Murodova N., O'zbek tilida fitonimlar: BMI
3. Бурмистрова Т.Н. «Сакральная фитонимия: лингвокультурологический аспект: Автореф. дисс. ...канд. филол. наук: 10.02.01. Екатеринбург, 2008. – 24 с.
4. Веселовский А.Н. Из поэтики розы. Художественно-литературный сборник. СПб., 1898. – 5 с.
5. Достоевский Ф.М. Белые ночи: Роман и рассказы. М.: Советская Россия, 1987. – 224 с.